

INFLUENCE OF DIGITAL SOCIAL MEDIA IN WRITING AND SPEAKING OF STUDENTS

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Annotation: The development of digital social media has significantly altered 20th century society. This new technology holds a lot of weight as a new tool for students and teachers to establish social bonds. The goal of this article is to determine how digital social media affects speaking and writing, how they inspire students to develop their productive skills, and to what extent SNS are helpful to students in developing their English language.

Key words: facebook, twitter, yahoo messenger, google plus, digital social networking, artificial perception, social circle

Annotatsiya: Raqamli ijtimoiy tarmoqlarning rivojlanishi 20-asr jamiyatini sezilarli darajada o'zgartirdi. Ushbu yangi texnologiya talabalar va o'qituvchilar uchun ijtimoiy aloqalarni o'rnatish uchun yangi vosita sifatida katta ahamiyatga ega. Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi raqamli ijtimoiy media talabalarning xorijiy tilda gapirish va yozish ko'nikmalariga qanday ta'sir qilishini, bu ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga qanday ilhomlantirayotganini va raqamli ijtimoiy tarmoqlarning ingliz tilini rivojlantirishda talabalarga qay darajada yordam berishini aniqlashdan iborat.

Kalit so'zlar: facebook, twitter, yahoo messenger, google plus, raqamli ijtimoiy tarmoq, sun'iy idrok, ijtimoiy doira

Аннотация: Развитие цифровых социальных сетей значительно изменило общество 20-го века. Эта новая технология имеет большое значение как новый инструмент для студентов и преподавателей для установления социальных связей. Цель этого artikля — определить, как цифровые социальные сети влияют на устную и письменную речь, как они вдохновляют учащихся на развитие продуктивных навыков и в какой степени социальные сети помогают учащимся развивать свой английский язык.

Ключевое слово: фейсбук, твиттер, мессенджер yahoo, google plus, цифровая социальная сеть, искусственное восприятие, круг общения

In the globalized world in which we live, people constantly accept new technology, information, lifestyles, languages, and other things. Additionally, young generations are increasingly influenced by digital social media, which are currently quite popular among them and widely used (e.g., Facebook, Twitter, yahoo chat, Google Plus). They believe that what they are doing in the realm of digital social media is current, and that if they adhere to the fads, others would see them as wise. However, today's young language learners are affected by digital social media in their language learning. Nowadays, young people interact with people mostly through digital social media, thus whether on purpose or not, they are following the trend of language learning.

It is true that digital social media plays a significant role in bringing individuals together, even when they are geographically separated. The younger generation enjoys adopting new trends and imitating others. Because of this, young people nowadays are driven by what others are doing on social media platforms and what activities are most popular. Younger generations prefer to watch others, copy what they do, strive to adopt their behaviours, and then demonstrate them in action. According to Bandura (1977), the majority of human behaviour is acquired through modelling and observation. By studying others, one develops an understanding of how new behaviours are carried out,

and this coded information later on acts as a guide for action.¹ In digital social media, people typically type down what they wish to present. Writing has changed from being a solitary pastime to being a very social form of communication (ibid). Prior to the Internet, the majority of people wrote to each other. Today, a single post can reach hundreds or thousands of individuals. In order to stay connected and be able to speak with a worldwide audience at any time, Chopra (2013) suggested that we look for laptop discounts with an eye on wireless connectivity. This has strengthened our writing abilities rather than diminishing them.² These days, people can readily connect with one another via digital social media, but they still choose speaking and writing as their primary forms of communication. The writing and speaking styles of today's youth are evolving. Both in writing and speech, they use shorthand, poor language, and symbols on SNS to convey their ideas. Additionally, these kinds of habits have an effect on how they write and talk in formal settings. SNS does not only have a negative effect on how people write and speak; it also encourages young people to learn new languages and helps them become more proficient in English. Therefore, the main goal of this essay is to determine how students' use of digital social media affects their oral and written communication, as well as how it encourages them to work on their English. The young of today are changing how they write and speak. They communicate their views on SNS using shorthand, poor grammar, and symbols both orally and in writing. Furthermore, these behaviours have an impact on how people speak and write in formal contexts. SNS influences people's writing and speaking styles negatively, but it also inspires young people to study new languages and improves their English language skills. Determining how students' use of digital social media influences their oral and written communication as well as how it motivates them to practice their English is the main objective of this article. These days' youth frequently utilize social media sites like Facebook, Twitter, Google Plus, Skype, and Yahoo Messenger. Students can communicate with their friends, family, and others because

¹ Bandura, A. (1977). *Social Learning Theory*. Englewood Cliffs, N.J: Prentice-Hall, page 22.

² Chopra, K. (2013, September 17). *The Effects of Social Media on How We Speak and Write*. *Social Media Today*.

to the popularity of texting and the proliferation of smart phones. Through their conversations on social media, people are learning new languages since they have the opportunity to interact with people from various countries. Teen users currently make up 80% of social media users, and they engage in a wide range of online communication techniques such as Netspeak, excessive abbreviation, and slang. Therefore, it is obvious that our real-world social lives have changed. Digital social networking platforms have been helpful in building a bridge between people and providing a forum for communication. A huge group of people may be kept in touch with via social networking platforms. In order to stay in touch with their friends and interact with their peers, students have embraced this new form of communication. Since educators and students now communicate via social networking sites, communication is rapidly evolving. Therefore, it's crucial to emphasize how teachers may support their pupils in using social networking sites to their advantage and develop their productive skills. Therefore, this research study suggests that if the teachers as well as the students utilize the digital social media in proper way it will be beneficial for them to enhance their English language.

Positive impacts of SNS

Facebook, Twitter, and Google Plus are just a few examples of the digital social media that are "impacting education significantly more dramatically than the traditional word-filled web page" (Eastment, 2007).³ According to Boyd (2007), teenagers and young adults have embraced these websites in particular as a method to interact with their friends, share knowledge, reinvent their selves, and highlight their social lives.⁴ Flad (2010) claims that because teenagers have access to social networking sites on their own cell phones throughout the day, communication is now instantaneous.⁵

³ Eastment, D. (2007). How do you keep up-to-date? *Elt Journal*, 61(2), 187- 189. doi:10.1093/elt/ccm016

⁴ Boyd, D. (2007). Why youth (heart) social network sites: The role of networked publics in teenage social life. *MacArthur Foundation Series on Digital Learning Youth, Identity, and Digital Media Volume*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press. 1-26.

⁵ Flad, K. (2010). The influence of social networking participation on student academic performance across gender lines.

Negative Impacts of SNS

Bunce (2010) claimed that speaking with someone face-to-face was preferable for language acquisition since "slow typing might greatly hamper language output, negotiation, collaboration, and therefore noticing." "The fact that online chat rooms are visual by nature is a significant characteristic."⁶ Chat discussions display both written and spoken language characteristics. Herring (1996) claims that while chat occurs in the written medium (words are typed on a keyboard and read from a screen), it generally consists of shorter, incomplete, 15 grammatically simple, and frequently incorrect (grammar and typographical errors) sentences, much like spoken language, especially unplanned speech.⁷

Conclusion

Digital social networking platforms have been helpful in building a bridge between people and providing a forum for communication. A huge group of people may be kept in touch with via social networking platforms. In order to stay in touch with their friends and interact with their peers, tertiary students have embraced this new form of communication. Since educators and students now communicate via social networking sites, communication is rapidly evolving. The importance of emphasizing how teachers may assist their pupils in utilizing the advantages of social networking sites to enhance their productive abilities cannot be overstated.

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